

A Study on the Coral Reefs of India

by Naw Jocelyn, Resource Person,

Department of Geography,

M.G. Govt. College, Mayabunder - 744204

Introduction :

Coral reefs are a dazzling sight. They are home to about a quarter of all marine life like fishes, crustaceans and other species. The variety of this habitat may be staggering, but the true attraction is the stunning colours that mesmerise all who have seen it. The secret to this astonishing spectrum of colours is in the corals themselves. These tiny creatures use minerals from the seawater to develop hard exoskeletons, made of calcium carbonate. Coral reefs are found in a wide range of environments, where they provide food and habitat to a large range of organisms as well as providing many other ecological goods and services. Warm-water coral reefs, for example, occupy shallow sunlit, warm, and alkaline waters in order to grow and calcify at the high rates necessary to build and maintain their calcium carbonate structures. Coral reefs have declined by 50% since 1950, partly because they are sensitive to water conditions. They are under threat from excess nutrients (nitrogen and phosphorus), rising ocean heat content and acidification, over fishing (e.g., from blast fishing, cyanide fishing, spear fishing on scuba), sunscreen use, and harmful land-use practices, including runoff and seeps (e.g., from injection wells and cesspools)

Types of Coral Reefs:

1. Fringing Reefs :

Fringing reefs grow near the coastline around islands and continents. These

types of reefs are the most common type we see and are considered to be the youngest of the 3 types of coral reefs. They are separated from the shore by shallow lagoons. The first stage of the formation is when the coral larvae attach itself to rocks or soil near the coasts. In certain parts of the world, they tend to form where volcanoes have also formed due to the shallow sloped walls being ideal to make shore reefs. The larvae become polyps and excrete calcium carbonate, which forms their exoskeleton. The secreted calcium carbonates sediments on the rocks and provides a substrate for more polyps coming to attach themselves.

2. Barrier Reefs :

As the name states, these reef types border along coastlines with a very wide and deep lagoon separating the two structures. The term “barrier” comes from the more shallower coral that sticks out of the water and creates a barrier or wall-like structure. One of the most famous and largest barrier reefs is “The Great Barrier Reef” in Australia. This reef is around 1200 miles and consists of many complex reefs making it up. This type of reef is formed when the fringing reefs slowly combine with each other and form a borderline along the coast. The calcium carbonate structures attract more polyps and the spaces are filled up. It forms a line along the coast and a ring around an island. Large barrier reefs are the rarest type of coral reef and only seen in a select few places on earth such as Belize and parts of the Southern Pacific Ocean. Smaller barrier reefs are seen in places where islands are in an earlier stage of becoming submerged.

3. Atoll Reefs :

Formation of an atoll according to Charles Darwin Atolls or atoll reefs are a more or less circular or continuous barrier reef that extends all the way around a lagoon without a central island. They are usually formed from fringing reefs around volcanic islands. Over time, the island erodes away and sinks below sea level. Atolls may also be formed by the sinking of the seabed or rising of the sea level. A ring of reefs results, which enclose a lagoon. Atolls are numerous in the South Pacific, where they usually occur in mid-ocean, for example, in the Caroline Islands, the Cook Islands, French Polynesia, the Marshall Islands and Micronesia. Atolls are found in the Indian Ocean, for example, in the Maldives, the Chagos Islands, the Seychelles and around Cocos Island. The entire Maldives consist of 26 atolls.

Conservation and management of Coral Reef areas in India :

The protection of coral reef has been stressed under Wildlife Protection act, 1972 and Environmental Protection Act, 1986 and Coastal Regulation Zone Notification (CRZN) of 1991 coming under it. Other acts like Indian Forests Act, 1927, Forest Conservation Act, 1980 and Indian Fisheries Act also offer a sort of relief in the conservation of Coral reefs of India. But there is no separate legal status for coral conservation even under Wildlife Protection Act. The State forest department, fisheries departments and recently the state coastal management authority at the state level are taking up the responsibilities for coral reef conservations in India. Wildlife Protection Act include the protection of major ecosystems, there is no direct stress on coral reef conservations.

Distribution of Coral Reefs in India :

India has a coast line of nearly 8129 km but the reef formation is restricted to four major centres, viz. Gulf of Kutch, Gulf of Mannar, Lakshadweep and Andaman and Nicobar Islands. In India, the reefs are distributed along the east and west coasts at restricted places. Fringing reefs are found in Gulf of Mannar and Palk Bay. Platform reefs are seen along the Gulf of Kachchh. Patchy reefs are present near Ratnagiri and Malvan coasts. Fringing and barrier reefs are found in Andaman and Nicobar Islands. The Lakshadweep is the only atoll formation of our waters. The total area of coral reefs in India is estimated to be 2,375 sq.km.

Conclusion :

Unfortunately, coral reef ecosystems are severely threatened, some threats are natural, such as diseases, predators, and storms and other threats are caused by people, including pollution, sedimentation, unsustainable fishing practices, and climate change, which is raising ocean temperatures and causing ocean acidification. Indian Government has also created mechanisms such as the National Coastal Zone Management Authority (NCZMA) and State Coastal Zone Management Authority for the protection of coastal and marine areas. Despite such efforts, a dedicated coral protection program is lacking in India and this is affecting the coral protection programs conducted by concerned state governments.

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